

Working capital management, Liquidity and Financial Performance: Context of Kenyan SME's

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Abstract: Working capital is all about management of short-term assets and liabilities of an organization in order to enhance profitability and avoid insolvency situations. This paper appraises the linkage between working capital management, liquidity and financial performance in Kenya with a keen interest on small and medium enterprises. The analysis is based on the desk review of the literature surrounding the stated subject area. One of the observations that was made was that poor working capital management can lead to collapse of even the most profitable corporations. Most of the literature analyzed clearly observes that, there is a close connection between working capital management and profitability. Liquidity, firm size, leverage and other financial ratios are also important factors which form part of working capital management.

Key Words: Working capital management, Liquidity, Financial performance, profitability, SME's

1.0 Background of the study

Working capital is concerned with management of current assets and current liabilities of an organization. It can be defined as assets which, during the course of business operations, they can easily be converted into cash within a period of one year without suffering an attenuation in value and interruption of the operations (Delima, Impact of Working Capital Management on Firm's Profitability: A Study on Listed Companies in Sri Lanka, 2020). The main objective of working capital management is to provide an assurance to companies about the going concern in terms of the daily operations and meeting their commitments as and when they arise. (Ndagijimana, 2014).

Analytically, it has been understood that excessive availability or lack of current assets in a company is not a problem as long as there is adequate planning and control of working capital, most firm directors usually involved financial experts with the knowledge and professionalism to determine the efficient working capital requirements for their companies. (Nyeadi, Sare, & Aawaar, 2018). Over the years, the aim of the working capital management has had to be reevaluated in the present narrative, as a result, if the old model perspective regarded working capital solely "a positive component of the balance sheet", later, the modern view considered working capital a "drag on financial performance" (Botoc & Anton, 2017)

Being a vital composition of corporate governance, working capital administration considerably mirrors the operation magnitude of the whole initiative, basically representing the foundation of endurance and growth of firms. (Han, 2021). According to (Han, 2021), effective working capital management can benefit from the increased earnings as risks mitigation while at the same time upholding the solvency anticipations of the firms.

More research needs to be conducted in regard to working capital management and to greater extend the determinant factors effects on financial performance since they are of high concern to legislators, intellectuals and industry owners due to the sensitivity of this phenomena (Botoc & Anton, 2017). In addition, (Botoc & Anton, 2017) notes that speeding up of industry operations have a tendency to expand the quantity of working capital, that is, produce extra financial limitations for upcoming ventures. In case these modern ventures are funded through leverage, this will cause an increasing leverage ratio and consequently a rise in financial hazard. Besides that, in the course of a depression or in a continually rising prices of commodities scenario working capital has a contradictory tendency to grow (Botoc & Anton, 2017)

Finance theory specifies the sound working capital management can impact financial performance and therefore financial stability of various enterprises. (Murigu, 2019). With the ravaging Covid- 19 pandemic, the fact to place in is serious lens is that in eras of financial distress, some of the suitable resolutions to emancipate from financial difficulties is to make proper choices concerning working capital management strategies. (Zimon & Tarighi, 2021). In the modern dynamic and fluctuating global economy, Zimon and Tarighi, (2021) notes that the choices on working capital management policies are some of the imperative responsibilities for company managers since they can perform a significant part in refining the financial state of firms in periods of distress. Decreasing the quantities of resources bound up in working capital,

companies can increase its reserves for other useful purposes and long-term investments (Botoc & Anton, 2017). Further, Botoc & Anton, (2017) found out that joint venture capital is the basis on which useful working capital management promotes higher firm operations. Furthermore, (Botoc & Anton, 2017) emphasized that effective working capital management may contribute to a new source of profitability on funds within the company, which consequently would be invested in a higher productive venture and portfolios to maximize the shareholders' funds, the main objective of the company.

2.0 Problem Statement

Working capital management is critical in unindustrialized economies, where the volatile conditions in the commercial sector and the unforeseen factors related to the economic situation can lead to severe general price instability (Boisjolya, Conine, & Donald, 2020). In the case of Kenyan economic background, SMEs face substantial challenges in as far as acquiring the credit facilities, which is strongly placed on the banking system, and also in out sourcing the sources required to finance their investments in their businesses. The problems in the small marketers are even more patent in the manufacturing sector, especially at this point where businesses tend to have a greater requisite for capital. (Sensini, 2020).

Working capital management has for a long time played a leading role of enabling the success of companies in recent decades. The working capital management gained momentum as a result of global financial crisis and the downfall of several major corporations such as "Lehman Brothers, Worldcom, Enron, and Bear Stearns". (Terreno, Pérez, & Sattler, 2020). Generally, neoliberalism and rapid technological evolution lead to high competition among business enterprises.

Working capital management therefore becomes critical in for achievement of the day-to-day business operations. Effective working capital management is also important since it is associated with the firm's financial performance. Maintaining adequate financial resources is a key at any moment for businesses (Kulo, Joshua, & Obeng, 2020). The working capital management concept, being a process of regulating the short-term resources, is worth being analyzed. WCM also manages liquidity by ensuring that it's maintained at reasonable level so as to achieve profitability of firms.

3.0 Methodology

Working capital is one of the critical aspects of business management, especially when it looking at solvency issues. The main objective of this study was to critically analyze the literature around working capital management, liquidity and financial performance. The study employed a derived or compiled data methodology. This paper is basically a desk review and/or literature review, with a view of making conclusions about the observations from the literature.

4.0 Literature Review

According to the perspective of the factors determining working capital management, the firm's categorical approach and the external economic atmosphere equally will influence a company's overall plan on working capital management. Various firms may adopt enhancement techniques and still face unstable conditions; therefore, the firm should always employ a working capital that resonates well with its mode of procedures. (Han, 2021)

As a result of the vibrant continuing argument between theory and practical pertaining to the

correlation between working capital and profitability, (Botoc & Anton, 2017) found out that the outcomes are pertinent for both researchers and specialists. The outcomes to some extent strengthen the contemporary point of view of working capital and may perhaps support the rationales for potential theories and research in the future.

4.1 Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC)

Cash conversion cycle (CCC) is an important technique used to estimate the level of efficiency of working capital management. Cash conversion cycle can be defined as the duration from the time of purchases of either raw materials and/or goods until the time accounts receivables are realized. (Delima, 2020) observed that CCC had negative correlation with profitability. He further stated that working capital management has significant impact on firm's profitability of listed companies in Sri Lanka. In his study the components of working capital management (WCM) included Number of Account Receivable Days, Number of Inventory Days and Number of Inventory Days. The findings by Delima (2020) were similar to another study by (Elangkumaran & Nimalathan, 2016) who observed that WCM had a significant impact on profitability of listed manufacturing companies in Sri Lanka. The study was also based on the principles of CCC.

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Various past analyses recorded an inverse correlation between working capital management and company profitability (Botoc & Anton, 2017). In his formative paper, Deloof (2003) evaluated an example of huge Belgian non-financial firms involving the era 1992–1996 and noticed an inverse linear relationship between cash conversion cycle (CCC) and operational performance determined by aggregate working revenue (Botoc & Anton, 2017) in which a negative relationship between working capital management and profitability is partly established for listed firms from CESEE region.

Delima (2020) who examined the effects of WCM on profitability of Sri Lankan listed firms. In addition, observed a significant negative correlation between “net operating profitability and the average collection period, inventory turnover in days and average CCC”. Debt ratio insignificantly positively related to profitability. In a study by (Althaqafi, 2020) on the effects of WCM on firm’s profitability, they established that a significant negative relationship exists between profitability and number of Accounts receivable components and Cash Conversion Cycle. However, an insignificant positive correlation was observed with inventory and Accounts Payable. Other significant control variables observed were financial leverage, sales growth, current ratio and firm size which had an effect on

the business’s profitability. WCM and profitability relationship might depend on the firms’ WCM strategy. According to (Altawalbeh M.A.F, 2020) ; a firm that adopts an aggressive WCM approaches, “usually has a negative relationship between components of WCM and profitability, and should expect profitability to be positively related”.

4.2 Liquidity

Liquidity is one of the key elements of working capital management. Liquidity is basically measured using current ratio and quick (or acid test) ratio. Current ratio is determined by dividing the current assets with current liabilities, while quick ratio is obtained by dividing current assets net of inventories by current liabilities. Under normal circumstances, a Current Ratio of 2:1 and a quick ratio of 1:1 is considered to be the standard to indicate sound liquidity position of a firm. A study by Khan (2016) observed that Small Manufacturing Enterprises operates below the stated standards therefore bearing a higher risk of facing liquidity and solvency challenges.

It is critical for an organization to maintain a balance between liquidity and profitability while conducting its day-to-day operations. Failure to maintain such a balance leads to the risk of insolvency. “Risk can be minimized by maintaining a higher level of current assets or working capital”. Further, firms, “which adequately plan its cash, inventory, sundry debtors have fewer problems of control than one, which operates without effective policies in these areas” (Khan, 2016).

From the previous studies, it is evident that strategic management of working capital encompassing sound decision making, proactive control of current assets movements, effective Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) and timely

settlements of current liability obligations as and when they fall due leads to stability in operations, predictability in earnings and mitigation of insolvency risks.

4.3 Working Capital Management and financial performance

The noticeable narrative is that Companies don't establish the factual worth of appropriate administration of working capital and in Such a regard, stress more on non-current investment decisions (Islam & Nazneen, 2013). Financial managers in various firms needs to be well conversant with the factors determining working capital management and thereby base their decisions in consideration of such factors in a deliberate attempt to achieve optimal level of working capital.

To achieve a sound working capital management strategy, it is essential to determine the critical mechanisms influencing WCM and enhancing the increase in earnings (Bashir, et al., 2018). However, the analysis and subsequent determination of such parameters that would curtail risks and foster profitability has been a thorn in the flesh of many firms, necessitating some to turn to the adoption of sensitivity analysis techniques and to a certain degree, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) settling on a trial-and-error method attributed to lack or expensive cost of consultation from professional financial experts. Sensitivity analysis adopts a special and an effective method that in contemporary global business, it is possible to determine the impacts on an undertaking as well as detecting variations in on several factors, thus aids in defining the aspects reflected as the main determination for the system (Iqbal, Hussain, Khalique, & Tabassum, 2020)

It has been established that under optimal level of working capital, it is said that there exists an effective management of working capital in the company insinuating the possibility of a positive correlation between working capital and profitability of the firm (Islam & Nazneen, 2013). The problem grounds on the overall objective of a firm which is maximization of shareholders wealth, in which WCM is the key determinant of the company's profitability, balancing and maintaining it at optimal level is usually the greatest undoing of many firms. That notwithstanding, it should be noted the firms 'profitability does not necessarily become a yardstick to measure the efficiency WCM and conclusively presume that the firm is operating at the optimal working capital level.

Investment in the eras of financial instabilities can prove much lucrative due to provision of more profit-making avenues against a substantial risk, moreover, companies can maximize profitability by growing their portion of the market (Zimon & Tarighi, 2021). In their study, they established that a substantial decline in investment in the times financial distress is not the consequence of a deficiency of invention and ingenuity in the industry, but instead the deficiency of credit provision of financial organizations to firms.

Firms that adopt a highly ambitious working capital policies, as a result, concentrating on working capital management tends to increase trades margin, and profitability, where once the optimum point is achieved, extra investments in working capital can lead to shortfalls in profits (Botoc & Anton, 2017).

4.4 SMES and Kenyan Perspective

The backbone of any country's economy is majorly supported by SMEs. Due to its significant impact on both social and economic development,

the micro and medium-sized business precinct is well recognized across the globe. For instance, the Garissa SMEs recorded a decline in net income for the period 2016-2020 with declining growth of ROA of 12.5% in 2016 to below 8.3% in 2020 (Ahmed & Mwangi, 2021).

Ostensibly, the challenges plaguing firms in their resolve to create an appropriate equilibrium between surplus and shortage of working capital and deficiency of suitable WCM undertaking ultimately affects earning capacity of the firm. (Mbathi, Mwambia, & Makena, 2021). Handling the working capital efficiently promotes the earnings of an enterprise, hence the CCC and its determinants specifically, inventory days, sales unpaid and account payables' payment period, were linked with the company's financial performance as the main contributor to the research gap (Murigu, 2019).

Imperatively, Working Capital is essential in any firm since it sustains the capacity of the firm's liquidity, expands the company's probabilities of existence in an extreme rivalrous setting, promises creditworthiness of the enterprise and fosters increase in earnings (Mbathi, Mwambia, & Makena, 2021). Murigu, (2019) found out that the association that occurs between financial performance of the firm and debtor variations in an era of a financial predicament is in such a manner that various companies must not sustain their debtors accounts at minimum amount so as to adventure profitability during the era of crisis. A business concern cannot operate efficiently without proper management of short-term resources such as receivables, cash, payables and inventory in order to honor its financial obligations when they fall due. Scrupulous management of receivables' collection period is quite important and ought to be prudently controlled. Ahmed and Mwangi, (2021)

established that financial performance of organizations is positively correlated to accounts receivable. They concluded that, business managers should craft good credit plans in order to improve monitoring of receivables' balances to ensure better financial performance (Ahmed & Mwangi, 2021).

Working capital management policies as employed by Kenyan firms plays a key role. For instance, Cash management policy helps a business to lessen or circumvent liquidity risks, increases the firms' production and investment income. Inventory management policy plays a major role in reduction of costs associated to inventories which in effect improves their financial performance. Receivables management policy also helps the businesses to grow its revenue turnover and lessen the borrowing costs. Payables management policy also enables a firm to increase production and avoid liquidity risks (Kiptoo, 2017). In order for the Kenyan firms to enjoy long survival in business, its critical for them to manage working capital effectively. The manner in which short term assets and liabilities are managed will have a direct effect on the supermarkets' profit and balanced liquidity (Ngari & Kamau, 2021).

5.0 Conclusion

Due to the contemporary Covid-19 pandemic, SMEs in Kenya resorted to a more conventional and less aggressive WCM strategy, which jeopardized not only their going concern but also stability of their operations (Zimon & Tarighi, 2021). That notwithstanding, with the new normal and slow but steady sprouting of the new SMEs and sustainability of the existing ones, there is need for more research on strategies to achieve WCM optimization.

WCM strategy has been emphasized by various scholars in their literature reviews and empirical studies as the key determinant of firm's liquidity and by a great extend the financial performance (Ngari & Kamau, 2021).

Working capital is a function of Liquidity and profitability. Ideally, working capital ratio as a measure of current assets over the current liabilities, is recommended to be between 1.5 and 2 according to financial experts. This literally depicts working capital as having a positive correlation with the current assets and a negative correlation with the current liabilities. However, a balance between the parameters needs to be achieved at the ideal ratio as recommended.

Understanding cash conversion cycle (CCC) helps organizations executives to manage resources more prudently therefore enhancing firm's financial performance expressively. The firm should therefore, ensure that the Inventory turnover existences is lessen to improve the net profit of the SMEs, whereas for the creditors and debtors' eras must take the edge off to diminish the liability and to ensure that there is advancement liquid in the daily operations of a business leading to significant impact on working capital. It was further observed that liquidity of a firm rises when the business is in a position to finance its debtors through increasing stock measure to meet the required firm satisfactions. Therefore, well managed working capital of a company can lead to effective financial performance of a firm, enhance profitability which helps to accomplish liquidity (Kulo, Joshua, & Obeng, 2020) and thus, positive relationship between the working capital (average collection periods, average payment period and cash conversion cycle) and the firm net profit was established.

Further study reveals that, working capital management demonstrates effects of liquidity components and productivity in a firm. Whereby when the companies current assets is high, there will be an increase in current ratio thus boosting the firm's financial performance while on the other hand, when there is a decrease in current liability companies rate of return increases. In addition, a firm cannot work well in absence of appropriate management of temporary assets such as the average collection period, inventory turn and net operating cycle so as to implement its investment commission when they go down overdue. Therefore, the study established a negative correlation between the average collection period, inventory turn, net operating cycle and firm cost effectiveness.

Another key consideration is working capital turnover ratio, which depicts the relationship between liquidity and financial performance by measuring the extent to which a firm utilizes every shilling worth of working capital conversion into sales (Warrad, 2013). Working capital turnover ratio can be determined by dividing sales over the average working capital. A high working capital turnover ratio indicates efficiency in the WCM since it contributes in boosting sales leading to increase in profitability, however, the turnover ratio should not be extremely high to an extend the firm faces the risk of being rendered insolvent.

Achieving and maintaining an optimal level of working capital is the ultimate indicator of a successful enterprise. At this point, the firm strikes a balance between liquidity and profitability proving that there is a significant relationship between WCM and liquidity on profitability.

The correlation between WCM, liquidity and profitability is significant and its impact on overall performance of the firm cannot be wished away. For a firm to maximize the shareholders wealth, there is need to focus on investments that bears maximum returns at the minimum cost possible without compromising the value of the business. Profits from the financial performance statements are always considered as a measure of performance, WCM is every so often overlooked. Nevertheless, just like a car engine that needs maintenance, regular service, and replacement of the worn-out parts, WCM is pivotal in driving the

operation of the business and profitability is only a comparison of the distance covered by the car. In the attempt of justifying the effect of working capital management on firm productivity, past research papers used control variables mainly firm size, prospect expansion, debt ratio, and other financial ratios, where much of the previous papers found a negative relationship between leverage and firm revenue earnings (Botoc & Anton, 2017). Moderation, coordination, efficiency and optimization of the WCM is a recipe to the desired results and the driver to the destination of the overall objective as depicted in the diagram below:

Figure 1: Relationship between variables

References

Ahmed, A. Y., & Mwangi, L. W. (2021). Working Capital Management and Financial Performance of Small and. *International Journal of Current Aspects in*

Finance, Banking and, Volume 4,(Issue 1),
56-71,. doi: ISSN 2707-8035

- Altawalbeh M.A.F. (2020). impact of working capital management on financial performance: evidence from Jodern. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance, and Management Sciences*, 10 (1): , 308-315. doi:SSN 2707-8035
- Althaqafi, T. (2020). Effect of inventory management on financial performance: evidence from the. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing, and Finance Research*, 8, 10, , pp.13-26.
- Bashir, Z., Arshad, M. U., Ghazali, A., Haider, A., Fazal, S., & AizazGoraya. (2018). An Empirical Analysis of Working Capital Management Attributes and Firm's Profitability Evidence from the Textile Sector of Pakistan. *Journal of Commerce, Accounting and Finance Management, Volume 1 Issue 2* , 1-22. doi: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3936363>
- Boisjolya, R. P., Conine, J. R., & Donald, T. E. (2020). Working capital management: Financial and valuation. *Journal of Business Research*,, 1- 8.
- Botoc, C., & Anton, S. G. (2017). IS PROFITABILITY DRIVEN BY WORKING CAPITAL MANAGEMENT? EVIDENCE FOR HIGH-GROWTH FIRMS FROM EMERGING EUROPE. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 1136-1155. doi:10.3846/16111699.2017.1402362
- County of Garissa Trade Report. (2017). *Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Garissa*.
- Delima, V. J. (2020). Impact of Working Capital Management on Firm's Profitability: A Study on Listed Companies in Sri Lanka. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 20(1), 42-58. doi:10.9734/AJEBA/2020/v20i130318
- Elangkumaran, P., & Nimalathan, B. (2016). The Impact of Working Capital Management on Corporate Profitability: Evidence from Listed Manufacturing Company of The Colombo Stock Exchange in Sri Lanka. *Accounting Governance & Corporate Sustainability: Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference*. doi:10.2139/ssrn.3733327
- Han, R. (2021). Empirical Study on Influence Factors of Working Capital and Turnover Ratio. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3833039>, 1-18.
- Iqbal, Z., Hussain, M., Khalique, M., & Tabassum, A. (2020). New Insight in Working Capital Determinants Making Sensitivity Analysis for Non-financial Listed firm's Evidence from Pakistan. *Journal of Managerial Sciences, Volume XI Number 04* , 1-22.
- Islam, M., & Nazneen, S. (2013). Efficiency in Working Capital Management and its Relationship with Profitability: Study on the Engineering Sector in Bangladesh. *The Jahangirnagar Journal of Finance & Banking, Volume-1*, 1-9. doi: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2979299>
- KENNON, J. (January 07, 2022). Working Capital.
- Khan, M. A. (2016). Working Capital Management and Its Impact on SMU'S Performance. *IJER © Serials Publications*, 13(5), 2059-2088. Retrieved from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3880184>

- Kiptoo, I. K. (2017). *Working Capital Management Practices And Financial Performance Of Tea Processing Firms In Kenya*. University of Embu.
- Kulo, I. I., Joshua, A., & Obeng, A. R. (2020). Effect of Working Capital Management on the viability of the company: A review in Sri Lanka on Listed Companies. *International Journal of Empirical Finance and Management Science, Vol. 02, (No. 03)*, 32-42. doi:ISSN 2706-803X
- Mbathi, V., Mwambia, F., & Makena, J. (2021). Effect of cash conversion cycle and inventory holding period on the profitability of small and medium enterprises in wote, makueni county. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research, Vol.9, 35-42*. doi: ISSN: 2053-4094
- Murigu, R. J. (2019). EFFECT OF WORKING CAPITAL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF HOTELS IN NYERI COUNTY KENYA. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Review, 13-84*.
- Ndagijimana, J. P. (2014). Factors Affecting Working Capital Management Practices In Small and Medium Enterprises in Nairobi. *Chandaria School of Business [2983]*, 13-55. doi:http://erepo.usiu.ac.ke/11732/83
- Ngari, A. R., & Kamau, C. G. (2021). Working Capital Management Cycle and Profitability of Household Supermarkets in Kenya: A Literature Review. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS), v(viii)*, 711-714. doi:[https:// dx.doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2021.5841](https://dx.doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2021.5841)
- Nyeadi, J. D., Sare, Y. A., & Aawaar, G. (2018). Determinants of working capital requirement in listed firms: Empirical evidence using a dynamic system GMM. ISSN: (Print) 2332-2039 (Online) *Journal homepage: <https://www.tandfonline.com/loi/oaef20>*, 1-14. doi:10.1080/23322039.2018.1558713
- Sensini, L. (2020). Working capital management and performance: evidence Canadian. *Journal of Administrative Sciences,, 16(1)*, 53-57.
- Terreno, D. D., Pérez, J. O., & Sattler, A. S. (2020). Working Capital Management and Profitability: Evidence from an Emergent Economy. *International Journal of Advances in Management and Economics*. doi:ISSN: 2278-3369
- Warrad, L. (2013). The Impact Of Working Capital Turnover On Jordanian Chemical Industries' Profitability. *American Journal of Economics and Business Administration, 5(3)*, 116-119. doi:10.3844/ajebasp.2013.116.119
- Zimon, G., & Tarighi, H. (2021). Effects of the COVID-19 Global Crisis on the Working Capital. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management, 1-18*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm14040169>